

Impact of Neurodevelopmental therapy in improving fine motor skills among children with Autism

Vikas Chandra Kushwaha¹, Sita Ram Pal²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Hearing Impairment, Faculty of Special Education,
DSMNR University, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Hearing Impairment, Faculty of Special Education,
DSMNR University, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India

Abstract:

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a range of complex neurodevelopment disorders, characterized by social impairments, communication difficulties, and restricted, repetitive, and stereotyped patterns of behavior. There are various degrees of fine motor skills deficits like inability to eat, inability to use a computer, difficulties in personal care tasks such as dressing and grooming, difficulties in holding pen or pencil in hand, difficulties in drawing line on paper, difficulties in turning pages, handwriting deficits, and difficulties in the writing process found along with problems in manual dexterity among children with Autism. Lacking of fine motor skills adversely affects writing, drawing as well as many functional activities involving the hands and arms directly affects academic activities. Motor skills especially fine motor skills among children with autism can be developed through innovative practices like Neuro Developmental Therapy (NDT), Sensory Integration Therapy (SIT). This paper highlights about the role of Neurodevelopmental therapy in improving fine motor skills among children with Autism. Various Approaches which are effective methods used as physiotherapy interventions and management to improve fine motor skills in children with Autism.

Key words: ASD, NDT, fine motor skills.

1. Introduction:

Autism referred to as autism spectrum disorder constitutes a diverse group of conditions related to development of the brain. About 1 in 100 children has autism (World health Organization, 2023, 29 March). Autism is considered a lifelong disorder, the degree of impairment in functioning because of these challenges varies between individuals with autism. (American Psychiatric Association, 2013) and Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a developmental disability that can cause significant social, communication and behavioural challenges, Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2021, April 29). Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is an inclusive term for children who have socio-communication impairments and restricted, repetitive patterns of behaviour along with hyper or hypo-reactivity to sensory input. (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth edition (DSM-5), American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Writing is a foundational skill

that can support and extend student learning across the curriculum. It allows the sharing of opinions, the demonstration of critical thinking skills, and the display of content knowledge. Miyahara et al.,(1997)in their report titled ‘Motor incoordination in children with Asperger syndrome & Learning disabilities’ which was published in Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders, October 1997, Volume 27, Issue 5, pg. 595-603, have found deficiencies in fine motor skills with delays in manual dexterity in children with ASD. Writing is critical for academic success, as it is the primary means by which students demonstrate their knowledge in school, and the major instrument that teachers use to evaluate academic performance (Graham & Harris, 2005). Writing has become an increasingly important element across curricular areas. However, many young children, including children with autism spectrum disorders (ASD), struggle with this key literacy skill. While it has been well-documented that many children with ASD have handwriting deficits, difficulties in the writing process, including planning, content generation, and revising text (Autism spectrum news, winter 2013 vol.5 no.3). Deficits in writing have been well documented study done by (Mayes & Calhoun, 2008), and found that 63% of students diagnosed with ASD also exhibited a writing disability. The academic development of children with autism spectrum disorders is important to investigate as it can provide opportunities for higher education, independent living, and successful employment in adulthood.

2. Review of related literature: Adrien, J.L. et al. (1993) observed hypotonia in children with autism spectrum disorder. Hypotonia found in children with ASD can affect a child’s ability to eat, write legibly, use a computer, turn pages in book and perform personal care tasks such as dressing and grooming. Mari, Castiello, Marks, Marraffa, & Prior, (2003) in their study titled ‘The reach-to-grasp movement in children with autism spectrum disorder’ published online in Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences, 358(1430), page 393–403, observed that autistic children showed differences in movement planning and execution, supporting the view that movement disturbances may play a part in the phenomenon of autism. They also have motor control issues in prehension, so that such fine motor skill deficits influence handwriting as well as many functional activities involving the hands and arms. Graham & Harris (2005), has written in his book titled ‘Writing better’ published by Brookers Publishing Co. at Baltimore that writing is critical for school success, as it is the primary means by which students demonstrate their knowledge in school, and the major instrument that teachers use to evaluate academic performance .Writing is a foundational skill that can support and extend student learning across the curriculum. It allows the sharing of opinions, the demonstration of critical thinking skills, and the display of content knowledge. Writing skills are directly helpful in curricular activities in the children with autism spectrum disorder. In a study by Provost B, Heimerl S, and Lopez BR,(2007) titled ‘Levels of gross and fine motor development in young children with autism spectrum disorder’ published in journal ‘Physical and occupational therapy in paediatrics’, vol.27,issue 3, page21-23 found that out of total 38 children with ASD, between age of 21 to 41 months, 50-73% of children have a delay in motor skills. Small muscles movements of the body refers to fine motor skills which is directly related to writing skills & as well as important in most academic activities. Mayes & Calhoun,(2003) in their article titled ‘Ability profiles in children with autism: Influence of age & I.Q.’ which was published in journal, Autism vol. 7 (10),

March 2003 reported that children with autism spectrum disorder also shows delay in graphomotor skills. Kushki A, Chau T, et al. (2011) reported his article titled ‘Handwriting difficulties in children with autism spectrum disorder: A scoping Review’ which was published in Journal of Autism & developmental disorders, vol.41, issue 12, page1706-1716, that impairments in many aspects of functional handwriting are associated with Autism spectrum disorders (ASD), suggesting a heightened risk of handwriting difficulties in children with ASD.

3. Rationale: For Autism, most of the researches have done in the area of communication, gross motor, language, and speech, social and behavioral aspects. Primarily inclusion of children with disabilities along with autism is a concurrent and secondly no study has been found which shows the improvement of fine motor skills through therapeutic interventions in Autism. Fine motor skills involves activities like – ability to eat, use a computer, personal care tasks such as dressing and grooming, holding pen or pencil in hand, drawing line on paper, turning pages, handwriting skills, activities of daily living and manual dexterity skills. Lacking of fine motor skills adversely affects activities of daily living, writing and drawing skills. The fine motor development of children with autism spectrum disorders can provide opportunities for independent living, higher education, and successful employment in adulthood. Various innovative Approaches and methods are available to improve the fine motor skills among the children with Autism.

Neurodevelopmental Therapy (NDT): Neurodevelopmental therapy is related to neuromotor and basically controls Postural tonus, Reflexes & reactions and Movement patterns of human body. One of the primary purposes of NDT is the facilitation of normal muscle tone in order to maintain normal postural and movement patterns as well as involve in activities. The neurodevelopmental therapy approach (NDT) is one of the most common intervention methods which utilized in the intervention of children with developmental dysfunction and first of all it was used in the therapy of children with cerebral palsy. Later, it was used in the intervention of many developmental disabilities. The NDT approach focuses on the normalization of hyper or hypotonic muscles, the specific handling intervention of equilibrium reactions & the child's movement and its facilitation. NDT is a popular therapy method within the intervention approaches of infants and children with neuromotor dysfunction (Bobath 1980, Harris 1981).

Objective of the Study:

To study the impact of Neurodevelopmental therapy on fine motor skills of dominant hand of children with Autism.

Research Question:

What is the impact of Neurodevelopmental therapy on Fine Motor skills of Children with Autism?

H01- There is no significant difference of neurodevelopmental therapy in improving drawing a straight line with pencil among children with autism.

H02- There is no significant difference of neurodevelopmental therapy in improving simulated page turning among children with autism.

H03- There is no significant difference of neurodevelopmental therapy in improving picking up small common objects among children with autism.

H04- There is no significant difference of neurodevelopmental therapy in improving stacking checkers among children with autism.

4. Methods

Subjects: Ten children from both sexes (06males, 04females) suffering from autism spectrum disorders (ASDs) participated in this study. Their age ranged from 8 to 15 years. This study was conducted in the period of 10 days (02 sessions per day), total of 20 sessions per child, in the month of October 2023. They were from the school of special needs.

Tool: Adapted Jebsen-Taylor Hand Function Test was used in the study in which domains like drawing a straight line with pencil, card turning, holding small common objects and placing of checkers were tested only with the dominant hand. The children were tested pre and post treatment to determine the impact of neurodevelopmental therapy in improving fine motor skills among children with Autism. Each child was evaluated and tested individually following the standard protocol.

NDT Treatment: A Neuro developmental therapy treatment program was conducted to all children who participated in this study. This program was conducted two sessions per day for 10 days (Total 20 sessions). Each child's particular test was individualized and guided by the therapist; the therapy was done in a large room with table and chair along with Jebsen-Taylor Hand Function Test kit. It was designed to encourage the kids to be active and get more comfortable with the sensory information they are receiving. The activities were set up to allow each of the senses to be used frequently during the session. The time recorded with the help of stop watch for different tasks given in the test. Each task was performed and tested only by the dominant hand.

5. Data collection and analysis: "t" test compare mean was used in this study.

6. Results:

H01- There is no significant difference of neurodevelopmental therapy in improving drawing a straight line with pencil among children with autism.

Table-1

Skill	Test	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t-value
DRAWING A STRAIGHT LINE WITH PENCIL	Pre-Test	10	38.7000	6.41266	2.02786	2.187
	Post-Test	10	32.4000	6.46701	2.04505	

Interpretation: The t-test was applied to measure the drawing a straight line skill with pencil. The mean scores of pre-test and post -test was found 38.7 and 32.4 respectively. The calculated t-value 2.187 is greater than the table value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. It reveals that there is a significant difference in both pre and post-test among the children with autism in performance of drawing a straight line skill with pencil. The result also indicates that the children with autism improving drawing skills through dominant hand. The t-value shows that there is a difference in drawing skills through dominant hand among the children with autism. Hence the null hypothesis no-1 is rejected. It means that in pre test children perform the skill in 38.7 seconds while after the treatment the respondent performs same task in 32.4 seconds, which clearly indicates that after taking NDT treatment, in the post test score respondents are taking less time to perform the same task. It shows that Neurodevelopmental therapy is impactful in improving fine motor skills among the children with autism.

H02- There is no significant difference of neurodevelopmental therapy in improving simulated page turning among children with autism.

Table-2

Skill	Test	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t-value
SIMULATED PAGE TURNING	Pre-Test	10	35.6000	6.88315	2.17664	2.194
	Post-Test	10	29.0000	6.56591	2.07632	

Interpretation: The t-test was applied to measure the simulated page turning skill. The mean scores of pre-test and post -test was found 35.6 and 29.0 respectively. The calculated t-value 2.194 is greater than the table value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. It reveals that there is a significant difference in both pre and post-test among the children with autism in performance of simulated page turning skills. The result also indicates that the children with autism improving simulated page turning skills through dominant hand. The t-value shows that there is a difference in simulated page turning skills through dominant hand among the children with autism. Hence the null hypothesis no-2 is rejected. It means that in pre test children perform the skill in 35.6 seconds while after the treatment the respondent performs same task in 29.0 seconds, which clearly indicates that after taking NDT treatment, in the post test score respondents are taking less time to perform the same task.It means that Neurodevelopmental therapy is effective in improving fine motor skills among the children with autism.

H03- There is no significant difference of neurodevelopmental therapy in improving picking up small common objects among children with autism.

Table-3

Skill	Test	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t-value
PICKING UP SMALL COMMON OBJECTS	Pre-Test	10	34.0000	7.94425	2.51219	2.228
	Post-Test	10	25.8000	8.50882	2.69072	

Interpretation: The t-test was applied to measure the picking up small common objects skill. The mean scores of pre-test and post-test was found 34.0 and 25.8 respectively. The calculated t-value 2.228 is greater than the table value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. It reveals that there is a significant difference in both pre and post-test among the children with autism in performance of picking up small common objects skills. The result also indicates that the children with autism improving picking up small common objects skills through dominant hand. The t-value shows that there is a difference in picking up small common objects skills through dominant hand among the children with autism. Hence the null hypothesis no-3 is rejected. It means that in pre test children perform the skill in 34.0 seconds while after the treatment the respondent performs same task in 25.8 seconds which clearly indicates that after taking NDT treatment, in the post test score respondents are taking less time to perform the same task. It shows that Neurodevelopmental therapy is helpful in improving fine motor skills among the children with autism.

H04- There is no significant difference of neurodevelopmental therapy in improving stacking checkers among children with autism.

Table-4

Skill	Test	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t-value
STACKING CHECKERS	Pre-Test	10	32.2000	8.03879	2.54209	2.241
	Post-Test	10	24.4000	7.51591	2.37674	

Interpretation: The t-test was applied to measure the stacking checkers skill. The mean scores of pre-test and post-test was found 32.2 and 24.4 respectively. The calculated t-value 2.241 is greater than the table value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. It reveals that there is a significant difference in both pre and post-test among the children with autism in performance of stacking checkers skills. The result also indicates that the children with autism improving stacking checkers skills through dominant hand. The t-value shows that there is a difference in stacking checkers skills through dominant hand among the children with autism. Hence the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. It means that in pre test children perform the skill in 32.2 seconds while after the treatment the respondent performs same task in 24.4 seconds which clearly indicates that after taking NDT treatment, in the post test score respondents are taking less time to perform the same task. It means that after taking Neurodevelopmental therapy treatment fine motor skills have improved among the children with autism.

7. Summary and Conclusion: By the interpretation of results it may be concluded that the Neurodevelopmental therapy was effective in improving fine motor skills of autistic children as it can provide opportunities for independent living, higher education, and successful employment in adulthood. In the same fashion NDT, SI therapy, and other interventions are also effective in minimizing the challenges faced in curricular and co-curricular areas of children with Autism. Children with autism can be skilled in functional independence and academic areas with the help of therapeutic intervention like NDT in very early stage with strong collaboration of parents, profession and other grass root level para-professional personnel.

8. Further discussions: This study was conducted to determine the impact of Neurodevelopmental therapy in improving fine motor skills of autistic children. The age

of the children included in this study ranged from eight to fifteen years old because later development is more affected in autistic children. Common findings in young children with ASD include increased joint laxity, hypotonia, clumsiness, apraxia and toe walking. Jebsen-Taylor Hand Function Test was used in the study in which domains like drawing a straight line with pencil, card turning, holding small common objects and placing of checkers tested, was used as a standardized tool for measurement of fine motor skills performed by children with ASD. In this study, the treatment procedures were selected based on the neurodevelopmental theory. This theory emphasizes that facilitation of normal muscle tone in order to maintain normal postural and movement patterns. The NDT approach focuses on the normalization of hyper or hypotonic muscles, the specific handling intervention of equilibrium reactions & the child's movement and its facilitation. NDT is a popular therapy method within the intervention approaches of infants and children with neuromotor dysfunction.

9. References:

- Adreïn, J.L. et al. (1993). Blind ratings of early symptoms of autism based upon family home movies. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry* 32:617-626
- Bobath, K. (1980). *A neurophysiological basis for the intervention of Cerebral palsy*. Philadelphia: Lippincott
- Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth edition (DSM-5). (2013). Arlington VA: American Psychiatric Association
- Graham, S., & Harris, K., (2005). *Writing better*. Baltimore: Brookers Publishing Co.
- Harris, S.R. (1981). Effects of neurodevelopmental therapy on motor performance of infants with Down's syndrome. *Developmental medicine & Child neurology* 23:447-483.
- Kushki, A., Chau, T., & Anagnostou, E., (2011). Handwriting difficulties in children with autism spectrum disorder: A scoping Review. *Journal of Autism & developmental disorders*, 41(12), 1706-1716.
- Mari, M., Castiello, U., Marks, D., Marraffa, C., & Prior, M. (2003). The reach-to-grasp movement in children with autism spectrum disorder. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 358(1430), 393-403.
<http://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2002.1205>
- Mayes, S.D., & Calhoun, S. L., (2003). Ability profiles in children with autism: Influence of age & I.Q., *Autism*, 7, 65-80.

Mayes, S., & Calhoun, S., (2008). WISC-IV & WIAT-II Profiles in children with high functioning autism. *Journal of autism. Journal of Autism & developmental disorders*, 38 (3), 428-439.

Miyahara, M., Tsujii, M., Hori, M., Nakanishi, K., Kageyama, H., & Sugiyama, T. (1997). Brief Report: Motor incoordination in children with asperger syndrome & Learning disabilities. *Journal of Autism & developmental disorders*, October 1997, Volume 27, Issue 5, pg. 595-69.

Provost, B., Heimerl, S., and Lopez, B.R., (2007). Levels of gross and fine motor development in young children with autism spectrum disorder, *Physical & Occupational Therapy in Paediatrics*, 27:21-36